

Distributed BSP Control for Low Earth Orbit Service Operations

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Abstract—We discuss a novel approach to manipulation and transport of satellites for Low Earth Orbit service operations and present our simulation results. Our approach is based on cooperative manipulation principles and leverages on a Reynolds boids’ collective coordinated movement. The implementation exploits Belief Space Planning (BSP) to enforce the Reynolds’ flock rules and the compliance of the satellite’s exterior to perform grasping and transport of satellites from a lower to an higher orbit.

Index Terms—swarms of space robots, collective intelligence, cooperative autonomous grasping and transportation, soft space robots

I. INTRODUCTION

We perform grasping and transportation tasks in space by means of tick-like robots smaller than the object to be transported. This is a novel approach as so far manipulation in space has been performed by bulky arms or by humanoids or semi-humanoid robots. The approach is inspired by ant manipulation and transport behaviors. It is based on a simple extension of Reynolds’ boids based on a simple BSP (Belief Space Planning) control driving a little swarm of space robots with simple compliant ‘gripping components’. This work extends previous work in the underwater domain to the Low Earth orbit domain, [4]. The comparatively easy implementation underwater provides a straightforward approach to test the proposed platform before the more expensive testing in space, as they did in the EU project Eurorobot,[1].

Our work is part of an ambitious long term research programme aiming to develop a robust reconfigurable bioinspired production facility of solar panels and other artifacts in the Low Earth Orbit, an artistic render is given by Figure 1a. The task addressed in this paper is described in Figure 1b. A group of little robots grasps a bigger satellite on a lower orbit and moves it on an higher one.

II. METHODOLOGY

Transport robots are constituted by an approximately spherical body, equipped with suitable actuators (mechanical configuration and little rockets) and sensors to support their 6

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Fig. 1: Concepts: (a) Application environment (b) The task: moving a satellite from a lower to an higher orbit

DoFs motion in space (complete attitude control), with no kinematic chains or joints in-between. They have compliant bumpers and simple grippers and are quipped with a camera in the virtual ‘palm’ in between the ‘grippers’. The compliant soft materials provide the necessary compliance in order to perform the desired manipulation and transport operations and to avoid damaging delicate satellite surfaces. Softness also improves grasping stability by adapting the grippers of the different robot-satellites during the cooperative manipulation and transport tasks. They have 6 DoF-motion in space and can communicate and cooperate together to perform their tasks.

implemented on each vehicle used to keep the distances. The swarm behavior models were constructed in accordance with the methodology suggested by the authors in previous work [4], building on [2]. Belief Space Planning methods enable the simultaneous reduction of uncertainty and attainment of the desired state, as measured by the covariance of the state estimate measure. These attributes render them exceptionally well-suited for carrying out tasks in unstructured environments that are marked by substantial levels of noise like in case of not modeled compliant robots.

In our scenario, the autonomous robots in charge of moving the satellite from an orbit to an higher one follow the same trajectory, like a Reynolds’ flock together with the grasped satellite object that must be transported. They do so by keeping a predetermined distance from the geometric center of the satellite. The distances are measured in terms of cross-track error and distance along the path. We implement the Reynolds’

Algorithm 1: BSP Algorithm

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1 Input:  $b_0, b_{goal}$  Output:  $u_{1:s}$ 
2 initBSP ();
3 for  $i = 1$  to  $N$  do
4    $(\tilde{m}_{1:s}, \tilde{u}_{1:s}) = \text{CreatePlan}(m_0, m_{goal});$ 
5   for  $j = 1$  to  $s - k$  do
6      $k = r + j;$ 
7      $u_t = \text{LQR}(\tilde{u}_t, \tilde{m}_t, m_t);$ 
8      $z_t = g(x_t) + \xi;$ 
9      $m_{t+1} = \text{EKF}(m_t, u_t, z_t);$ 
10    if  $\|\tilde{m}_t - m_t\| < thr_1$  then
11      while  $e_t > thr_2$  do
12         $\eta_t = \text{DriveVehicle}(m_t);$ 
13    else
14       $r = r + j - 1;$ 

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Fig. 2: Results

flocking model by means of a Belief Space Planning control of the trajectories. Reynolds [3] has shown that flocking behaviors can be achieved by enforcing a basic set of rules on individual agents:

- 1) *Separation* — prevent the close proximity of neighboring objects through short-range repulsion.
- 2) *Alignment* — adjust direction to match the average heading of nearby agents.
- 3) *Cohesion* — direct towards the average position of neighboring entities (long-range attraction).

The tick-like robot agents target the school of robot ‘fishes’ geometric center, which corresponds to the geometric center of the satellite to be grasped or transported, (rules 2, 3) and keep distance among themselves (rule 1). The compliance of bumpers/grippers on the robots’ surfaces allows to collectively grasp and transport the object (a passive member of the flock).

The BSP-based algorithm is summarized in Algorithm 1. The controller is assumed to know the state through a probabilistic density function $P(x)$. In these hypotheses, and assuming maximum likelihood of the observations, it can be proved that it is possible to derive by iteration a series of segments with an associated set of control actions by minimizing the cost function J

$$J(b_{\tau:T}, u_{\tau:T}) = \sum_{i=1}^k w_i \left(\hat{n}_i^T \Sigma_i \hat{n}_i \right)^2 + \sum_{t=\tau}^{T-1} \tilde{m}_t^T Q \tilde{m}_t + \tilde{u}_t^T R \tilde{u}_t \quad (1)$$

where $b_{\tau:T}$ is the subset of the state space, $u_{\tau:T}$ are the corresponding actions for a given state space trajectory, Q and R are weight matrices, and the n_i are the versors of belief space along which the optimization is performed. Finally, Σ_T is the covariance matrix at the end of the segment, and m_t^T the value of the mean of the Gaussian of the measures. The function J is minimized by a standard SQP (Sequential Quadratic Programming) algorithm; after this, a linear quadratic regulator is applied to move along the segments.

The adoption of LQR standard control improves the efficiency of BSP planning: the evaluation of the optimal control action for the system leads to the stabilization of the trajectory in spite of the nonlinear dynamics of the system.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND DISCUSSION

The performed experiments focused on two different tasks requested to the swarm: i) *cooperative transport*; ii) *cooperative grasping*. The experiments were performed in simulation in MATLAB on a standard Windows laptop PC. The simulation results of the cooperative transportation phase are shown in Figure 2. Figure 2(a) shows how the satellite is moved from a lower to a close higher orbit. Figure 2(b) illustrates in more detail the path followed by the group of robots with the satellite at the flock center. The distances of each vehicle from the grasped satellite during task execution is represented in Figure 2(c), while the mutual distances of the ‘grasping and transporting’ robots during task execution can be found in Figure 2(d).

For the cooperative grasping phase, a constraint has been added in the optimization procedure: each vehicle has to keep its own distance from the object below a grasping threshold.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The results of our simulation runs show the effectiveness of the method. In the future, we will utilize two-way mixed reality simulation to enhance the system design in preliminary underwater experiments. Subsequently, we will proceed with the implementation of real-world swarms in an underwater field settings. Our final objective is to test this system in space.

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